

Strathmore
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Deliverable

Guidelines for shipping and curation of data

Task 5f

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1 Module 1: Introduction to Data Security for Energy Planning

Course overview

This course provides a basic understanding of data privacy and security in the context of energy planning. It explores the legal framework, risks, and best practices to ensure secure and responsible data management.

Intended Learning Outcomes

By the end of this course, participants will be able to:

- Recognize the importance of data security in energy planning.
- Understand how legislation influences data security in Kenya.
- Identify risks associated with data sharing.
- Be able to use data classification

Course Structure

The course consists of three modules, each following a consistent format:

- Introduction: Overview of key themes in the module.
- Course content: In-depth exploration of the topic.
- Exercises: Practical activities for deeper understanding.

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2 Module 2: Data privacy and security in Kenya

Introduction

Data privacy and security refer to the protection of data concerning access, use, processing, and storage (Ramirez Rodriguez et al., 2024). For data security to be effective, protocols must align with legal requirements. This module examines Kenya's legal framework to understand its impact on data security and privacy, particularly in the context of energy data. The next module will explore data classification and governance mechanisms to enhance data protection strategies.

Legal Framework

The table below summarizes key legislation affecting data security in Kenya. The left column lists relevant laws, while the right column explains their impact on data security.

Table 1. Legislation influencing data security in Kenya

Legislation	Key Provisions
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|-----------------------------------|--|
| - The Constitution of Kenya, 2010 | - Article 31: Right to privacy
- Article 35: Right of access to information |
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| - County Governments Act, 2012 | - Ensures access to key information that shapes policy decision-making
- Protects the rights of marginalised groups and minorities to access information |
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- | | |
|--|---|
| - Access to Information Act, 2016
- Access to Information (General) Regulations, 2021 | - Defines rights and procedures for accessing information |
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- | | |
|--|---|
| - Data Protection Act, 2019
- The Data Protection (Registration Of Data Controllers And Data Processors) Regulations, 2021
- The Data Protection General Regulations, 2021 | - Establishes personal data protection standards, including processing, retention, and security |
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- | | |
|--------------------|---------------------------|
| - Energy Act, 2019 | - Regulates energy policy |
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The Access to Information (General) Regulations, 2021, and the Data Protection General Regulations, 2021, establish key guidelines for ensuring data security. The following are some key points derived from these regulations.

Key points: Access to Information (General) Regulations

Every organization, whether public or private, must appoint an Information Access Officer, responsible for:

- Proactively disclosing information and processing access requests.
- Ensuring that personal data is disclosed only with written consent.
- Keeping records of data processing activities.

For more details, please refer to *PART II - Information access officers* on the Access to Information (General) Regulations, 2021

Key points: The Data Protection General Regulations

- Personal data collection requires explicit user consent.
- Data can be anonymized or pseudonymized upon request.
- Personal data can only be processed within Kenya. Data can only be retained for a limited time
- Personal data can only be processed in Kenya

The following box outlines key concepts from the Data Protection Act related to data privacy and security. These concepts will be explored in more detail in the next module.

Box 1. Data Protection Act definitions (*Data Protection Act, 2019*)

- **Consent:** Any manifestation of express, unequivocal, free, specific and informed indication of the data subject's wishes by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifying agreement to the processing of personal data relating to the data subject.

- **Personal data:** any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person.

- **Sensitive personal data:** data revealing the natural person's race, health status, ethnic social origin, conscience, belief, genetic data, biometric data, property details, marital status, family details including names of the person's children, parents, spouse or spouses, sex or the sexual orientation of the data subject.

- **Identifiable natural person:** a person who can be identified directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social or social identity.

- **Profiling:** any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's race, sex, pregnancy, marital status, health status, ethnic social origin, colour, age, disability, religion, conscience, belief, culture, dress, language or birth; personal preferences, interests, behaviour, location or movements.

- **Pseudonymisation:** the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, and such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data is not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

Reflective exercise

Review **Data Protection General Regulations, 2021 (Part II, Sections 6-9)** and **Access to Information (General) Regulations, 2021 (Parts II-IV)**:

- Identify which procedures your organization follows and which ones it does not.
- What is one requirement you were previously unaware of?

3 Module 3: Data classification

Introduction

The previous module examined how the legal framework influences data security in energy planning. This module shifts focus to understanding the risks associated with data and how data classification can enhance security and privacy management.

Energy planning relies on diverse datasets, including information on energy generation, distribution networks, or generation costs. Classifying data depends on specific needs and contexts. The following exercise explores how different datasets can be categorized to improve data management.

Exercise

Classify the following datasets into 2-3 groups and justify your reasoning:

- Energy demand from households in Nairobi County.
- Cost of energy in every neighbourhood in Kitui County.
- Hourly demand load profile at the national level.
- Water inflows for hydropower dams.
- Energy consumption from hospitals in Mombasa.
- Marginal cost of energy generation at the national level.

Solution

For the previous exercise, there is no right or wrong answer. One way to classify the data could be by distinguishing between *national-level* and *county-level* datasets. It could also be categorized by *economic data* and *other types*. A more detailed approach could involve classifying the data into categories such as *cross-cutting issues* and *data for energy models*.

Classifying data by risks

One way to classify data is by assessing the risks associated with it. This approach allows for a comparison of which types of data carry higher risks and helps in designing protocols to protect this information, thereby reducing the risk of sharing it. This is the purpose of data classification. Data classification is a tool used to rank data based on the risks associated with it (Bhajaria, 2022). To understand how energy data can be classified, let's first examine some of the risks related to sharing energy data:

- **Commercial Sensitivity:** Competitors can use data for financial advantage. Knowing the location of an energy resource and its available quantity can be used to develop a business proposal.
- **Personal Privacy Risks:** Identifiable data can expose individuals.
- **Misinterpretation:** Data taken out of context may lead to incorrect conclusions.
- **Profiling:** Personal data can be used to profile certain groups.

From that list, two potential types of data that carry risks can be identified: personal data and commercially sensitive data. However, this does not necessarily mean these are the only groups.

Reflective exercise

Can you think about any other types of data that carry risks in your organization?

Solution example

For example, personal data could be divided into two groups: non-sensitive personal data and sensitive personal data, with the last one carrying higher risks when shared. Similarly, commercially sensitive data could be further divided into various groups if it is identified that they do not share the same risks.

Anonymisation and pseudonymisation

Despite the risks, sharing this information is essential for effective energy planning. Implementing the right methods can help minimize these risks, maintaining both individual privacy and protecting sensitive data.

Anonymisation

Anonymization involves removing identifying information to ensure that the original source cannot be traced (Jarmul, 2023). Some common methods include:

Adapted from Jarmul (2023)

Anonymisation	Description
Removal of columns or attributes	Delete the names, addresses, birthdates of a dataset
Aggregation of certain row attributes	Combine data in groups: 5 people live in this apartment building

Scrambling or other transformation methods to obfuscate individual characteristics	Mixing the row attributes from multiple rows so that no single row has its original values, but the overall distribution of values is unchanged
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Pseudonymisation

As defined in the *Data Protection Act (2019)* pseudonymisation is “the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, and such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data is not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person”. Some common methods include:

Adapted from Jarmul (2023)

Pseudonymisation	Description		Example
Masking	Applying a “mask” to the data that often replaces values with standard series of values	\$45,320	<PRICE> <\$4XXXX>
Tokenization (table-based)	Substituting sensitive data with unique tokens mapped through a lookup table, ensuring one-to-one replacement.	James Smith	<Jimmy Sanchez>
Hashing	Using a hash mechanism to make data less interpretable but still linkable	Kitui county	34dzks3nztw
Format-preserving encryption	Using a cipher or other cryptographic technique to replace the data with similar data. Often this is also linkable.	(0)30 4344 3333	(0)44 46227 1111

Disadvantages

These methods have certain limitations. For instance, when combined with publicly available datasets, they may still allow individuals to be identified. Consider the following example: a report detailing energy consumption by age group in an apartment building.

Average energy consumption by age in an apartment building

Age	Monthly energy consumption (kWh)
20-30	20,000
30-40	25,000
40-50	27,000
50+	60,000

This apartment building is primarily occupied by young people due to its proximity to a university. The building management publicly shares a list of residents along with their birthdates, accessible to anyone within the building. A person reviewing this list notices that only one resident is over 50 years old. By cross-referencing this information with an energy consumption report categorized by age group, they can deduce that this individual consumes more energy on average than other residents. This could suggest that they own high-energy-consuming electronics. While this insight may not seem inherently problematic, it demonstrates that combining multiple datasets can make a person identifiable, highlighting the disadvantages of anonymisation.

To address these limitations, differential privacy is a more robust approach to safeguarding personal data. The following resources provide some insights for further learning on this topic:

- <https://privacytools.seas.harvard.edu/differential-privacy>
- <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/dwork.pdf>
- <https://opendp.org/about>

Exercise: Identifying Risks in a Dataset

A county department requests access to the following dataset to analyse energy revenue.

Consider the following:

- What risks exist in sharing this dataset as-is?
- How would you classify this dataset (personal, sensitive, confidential)?
- Which attributes should be removed or modified?
- What are the potential consequences of sharing unmodified data?

Generation of energy plants

Manager of the plant	Contact of the manager	Generation	County	Revenue generation plant
James Smith	james@energy.ke	30,000	Kitui	\$50,000
Kate Perez	kate@energy.ke	20,000	Kilifi	\$10,000
Michael Wantama	michael@energy.ke	10,000	Mombasa	\$20,000
Grace Njeri	grace@energy.ke	100,000	Nairobi	\$80,000
Delight Omondi	delight@energy.ke	60,000	Tana River	\$30,000

3.1 Conclusion

Through this course, you have gained an understanding of:

- The role of data security in energy planning.
- The legal framework governing data privacy in Kenya.
- The importance of classifying and securing data.

By integrating these practices into your work, you contribute to a more secure and responsible energy planning process. If you have further questions, feel free to reach out!